

Una nueva clase de polinomios q -Apostol-Bernoulli de orden α

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Resumen

En este trabajo, en primer lugar se da una introducción de los números y polinomios de Bernoulli y sus q -generalizaciones. Luego se define una nueva clase de polinomios q -Apostol-Bernoulli de orden α y sus números correspondientes. Se obtienen representaciones explícitas, teorema de adición y fórmula diferenciales de esta nueva clase de polinomios.

Palabras clave: Polinomios q -Apostol-Bernoulli

A new class of q -Apostol-Bernoulli polynomials of order α

Abstract

In this paper, we first give an introduction of Bernoulli polynomials and numbers and their q -generalizations. We then define a new class of q -Apostol-Bernoulli polynomials of order α and corresponding numbers. We obtain explicit representations, addition theorem and differential formula for these newly defined class of polynomials.

Key words: q -Apostol-Bernoulli polynomials

Notations and Definitions

We shall use the following notations and definitions of q -theory (Gasper & Rahman [8])

The q -number $[x]_q$ and the q -number factorial $[n]_q!$, $n \in N$ are defined by

$$[x]_q = \frac{1-q^x}{1-q} \quad q \neq 1. \text{ and } [n]_q! = \prod_{j=1}^n [j]_q. \quad (1)$$

The q -shifted factorial (q -analogue of Pochhammer symbol) is defined as

$$(a; q)_n = \prod_{k=0}^{n-1} (1-aq^k), \quad n \in N \text{ with } (a; q)_0 = 1, \quad q \neq 1. \quad (2)$$